

Evaluating the usefulness of embedding phonetic representations into an authorship analysis-based framework for the comparison of spoken data

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Types of forensic speaker comparison (FSC) analysis

- FSC methods broadly split into human-led approaches and automatic approaches (with some combining the two).
- Gold and French (2019) survey of 39 labs – 41.2% used an ASR system, 58.8 did not.
- Morrison et al. (2016) survey of different methods used by Interpol law enforcement agencies

Feature levels in FSC

- Different types of features analysed in Auditory/Acoustic FSC analysis (Gold and French, 2011: 301-302).
 - **Segmental features** (vowels and consonants)
 - **Suprasegmental features** (F0, articulation rate, rhythmic properties of speech)
 - **“Higher order linguistic features”** (discourse or conversational patterns, grammar, lexis, syntax, morphology)
 - **Non-linguistic features** (pausing, breathing, throat clearing, laughter)

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Possibility of using **authorship analysis** methods to analyse this kind of information in speech?

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Is there a way of directly combining these two types of features in an analysis? And is this even worth doing?

Frequent-words analysis for forensic speaker comparison

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Highlights

- Frequent-words analysis has speaker-discriminatory power.
- Percentile rank is a simple but effective way to take typicality/rarity into account, in combination with the similarity of the recordings.
- A likelihood ratio system based on the transcription of spontaneous speech is presented.

“We showed that frequent-words analysis has speaker-discriminatory power. Our method is designed to work in a forensic setting, where little reference material may be available and results for any specific speech fragment should be explained and interpreted in court.”

(Sergidou et al., 2023)

Combing text-based and phonetic information

- “I go up the A40 to Carter Road” – Text level

- [ə̣ˌgɔ̣ ʊp̣ˈdʒiː eː fɔːtʃɛ tʰə kʰaːʔə rɜːtʰ] – Phonetic level

Feature	Realisation
GOAT vowel	[ɔ̣] - go (1 sec) [eː] - road (2 sec)
STRUT vowel	[ʊ] – up (1 sec)
START vowel	[aː] – Carter (2 sec)
happY vowel	[ɛ] – forty (1 sec)
Word-initial /ð/	[ḍ] – the (1 sec)
Intervocalic /t/	[ʔ] – forty (1 sec), Carter (2 sec)

The pilot study

- Focus on **filled pauses (FPs)**. Previous acoustic-phonetic work on this feature by Hughes et al. (2016: 1), which described FPs as having “*excellent potential as variables in forensic voice comparison cases*”.
- The authors also highlight that “*discourse structure also affects the frequency and type of FP used*” (Hughes et al., 2016: 3), but their analysis focussed on “*when they [FPs] occur in talk, irrespective of where they occur*” (Hughes et al., 2016: 6).
- **Research question:** Does the combination of phonetically transcribed FP plus “higher-level” linguistic information provide useful speaker-discriminatory power?
- **Data:** Tested using West Yorkshire Regional English Database (WYRED) (Gold et al., 2018). 30 speakers used in our pilot project. Only **Task 1 (Mock Police interview)** and **Task 2 (Telephone conversation with accomplice)**.

The pilot study

#	Transcription	Realisation
1	“eh”	FP with a mid-central or fronter/raised vowel realisation, such as [ɜ:], [ɛ:] or [e:]
2	“ah”	FP with a more open vowel quality realisation, around [a:] or [ɛ:]
3	“ehm”	FP as in (1) plus a bilabial nasal [m]
4	“ahm”	FP as in (2), plus a bilabial nasal [m]
5	“uh”	Vocalic hesitation marker with a quality that is different to those described in (1) and (2)
6	“uhm”	Vocalic hesitation marker with a quality that is different to those described in (1) and (2), plus a bilabial nasal [m]
7	“mm”	Hesitation marker containing only a nasal

The pilot study

ORIGINAL: “HES I work at Eugene's Hairdressers”

REVISED: “EH I work at Eugene's Hairdressers”

Authorship verification

vs

Same speaker or not?

Burrows' Delta

Word	NORM	author 1	author 2	NORM – author 1	NORM – author 2
a					
an					
all					
also					
some					
upon					

Cosine Delta

Most frequent 50 words

The cat sat on the mat and the dog sat on the chair.

N-gram tracing

A

Q text

B

N-gram tracing

B

Q text

N-gram tracing

N-gram tracing

A

$4/5 = 80\%$

B

N-gram tracing

N-gram tracing

word 2-grams

Jaccard coefficient

a d t b av w w wi y w 2 4 wi js d , 4 th
 d o n' u l e v t nt g a
 t d n x

Strugglin get babysitter at
 mo. Thats **y** never
 replied. Chris is goin **w**
 wayne x

Got go fetch milly. Val
 cant cope **w** her x

0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

$$J = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} = \frac{\text{number of features in } A \text{ and } B}{\text{number of features in } A \text{ or } B} = 1/2 = 0.5$$

Phi coefficient

Content masking

The cat sat on the mat and the dog sat on the chair.

The * * on the * and the * * on the * .

The N V on the N and the N V on the N .

Parts of Speech tags

Hesitations

eh ah ehm ahm ur um mm

No hesitations

vs

Only hesitations

vs

Both

Hesitations only word 2-grams

eh_i

P_eh

know_eh

eh_he

P_ah

ah_yeah

N_ah

ah_i

N_eh

eh_just

Next steps

- Just one feature looked at here and a limited amount of phonetic variation captured (compared to, for example, formant measurements).
- But what about features that are inherently categorical - **consonant** features?
- Hughes (2014) - more difficult for LR frameworks to deal with discrete data than continuous acoustic measures.
- Combining this discrete consonant phonetic variability with ‘higher-order’ linguistic features is the focus of our next piece of work in this area.
- More variation captured, greater discriminatory power? Ability to capture consonant variation within the LR framework?

Next steps

- Small research grant awarded by the International Association of Forensic Phonetics and Acoustics (IAFPA) to investigate this further.
- Focus on four discrete (but frequently occurring) consonant variables

Variable	Realisations
-ing suffix	[ɪŋ]
	[ɪn]
Intervocalic word-medial /t/	[t]
	[ʔ]
	[r]
Syllable-initial (voiceless) th-fronting/stopping	[θ]
	[f]
	[t]
Syllable-initial /l/	[l]
	[lʰ]

Thank you!

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